

AURORA shiny app

Streamlining Biodiversity Data Sharing

USER MANUAL

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The code for the AURORA Shiny App is stored in its [GitHub repository](#).

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INTRODUCTION

This user manual was designed to support the utilisation of the **AURORA Shiny App**, a comprehensive and user-friendly [online application](#) for converting unstructured biodiversity data into standards-compliant Darwin Core tables, paired with structured metadata, created as part of the AURORA – [Bringing Deep-Sea Biodiversity Data to Light](#) project. The manual provides a brief introduction to the application's main features and the Darwin Core guidelines. It then presents the requirements the raw dataset must meet before being imported to maximise the app's feature utility. The workflow is then detailed in the following sections of the manual.

For the **mobilisation and integration of biodiversity** data to be truly effective, data should follow the FAIR Principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016). **FAIR principles** are a set of guidelines to increase the **Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability** and **Reusability** of data and metadata for people and machines. These principles promote the **discovery, sharing, and re-use of data** in downstream studies, and ensure data is archived so they can be discovered and used by future generations (Wilkinson et al., 2016). For data to be FAIR and its integration effective, some standards need to be followed.

The considerable effort required, along with limited resources, capacity, and time, are commonly cited as factors that hinder the publication of biodiversity data (Benson et al., 2018; Chavan & Ingwersen, 2009; Tenopir et al., 2011). **The AURORA Shiny App addresses these barriers with a user-friendly interface that automates and systematises workflows, eliminating the need for coding expertise or for using multiple complementary tools. It is designed for researchers, data managers, and biodiversity projects seeking to enhance data quality, interoperability, and global visibility.**

AURORA APPLICATION

The main goal of AURORA is to assist with the **structuring and formatting of biodiversity datasets following Darwin Core (DwC) standards**, which, in brief, comprise:

- The structuring of the data in the appropriate Core table and Extension tables
- The mapping of column headers to match [Darwin Core terminology](#)
- The standardisation of the data, including:
 - Creation of standardised and unique identifiers for different events and occurrences (eventID and occurrenceID) from available fields when missing
 - date-related fields compliant with ISO 8601

- latitude and longitude in decimal degrees and referenced to [EPSG:4326](#)
- validated taxonomic information for both marine and terrestrial taxa based on [WoRMS](#) and [GBIF](#) taxonomy backbones
- measurements in the Extended Measurement or Fact extension (eMoF) table populated following controlled vocabularies ([BODC-NERC controlled vocabulary](#))

The **AURORA Shiny App** does not directly create a publishable Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A) file. Instead, it helps users generate the core data files (i.e., data tables) and compile the necessary metadata. This information can subsequently be used to create the DwC-A file using the Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT) software developed by GBIF - Global Biodiversity Information Facility (see [The OBIS Manual](#) and [GBIF IPT User Manual](#)).

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

No software installation is required. The **AURORA Shiny App** is accessible to the public via a web browser and requires only an internet connection.

WHAT IS DARWIN CORE STANDARD

Darwin Core is the most used **standard for biological data** (Van de Putte et al., 2021; Wieczorek et al., 2012). It includes a set of well-defined terms to structure data elements, enabling the **integration of data from various sources**. Compliance with DwC allows the **sharing of standardised information** on **sampling events, occurrences** (organisms in nature or in collections), **taxonomic checklists**, as well as on further information associated with the occurrence or events as extended **measurements or facts**.

Following DwC guidelines, data is organised in one **Core table** and optional **Extension tables** that provide additional information about the records in the Core table, each requiring a minimal set of fields. These text-based tables are organised in a **Darwin Core Archive**, i.e., a ZIP file also containing a XML descriptor file, with information on how the files are organised, and an XML file with the metadata, which provides information that describes the dataset itself and sampling methods, as well as authorship, license, and citation information (Fig. 1). The metadata is also standardised, following the Ecological Metadata Language. The Darwin Core Archive can be generated using the IPT developed by GBIF.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of a Darwin Core Archive, including the text-based tables containing the data (the core table and optional extension tables) and the descriptor and metadata XML files.

OBIS and EMODnet Biology accept both Event Core tables and Occurrence Core tables, while GBIF also accepts Taxon Core tables, when data is a checklist of taxa, i.e., a baseline inventory of taxa in a given context ([GBIF: Dataset classes](#)). [GBIF Registered Extensions](#) provides a list and descriptions of all **DwC extensions**. The extensions currently accepted by OBIS are the Occurrence extension, MeasurementOrFact, extendedMeasurementOrFact (eMoF), and DNADerivedData ([The OBIS Manual](#)).

EXPECTED GENERAL DATA STRUCTURE ACCORDING TO DwC

The **AURORA Shiny App** was primarily designed to assist in structuring raw data following the **DwC OBIS-ENV** or **Sampling Event** data formats; this includes generating an **Event Core** (also known as a Sampling-event core) as the primary table, which is then linked to an **Occurrence Extension** and an **eMoF Extension** table (Fig. 2). Additionally, the **AURORA Shiny App** supports the simpler **Occurrence Core** data format, where individual observations or specimens serve as the primary records without a hierarchical event structure.

Fig. 2. Representation of the relational databases expected as an output of the AURORA application, following the OBIS-ENV format.

Event Core tables provide **information about sampling events**, such as date and location, and are recommended when there is more than one occurrence per sampling event and when data include measurements associated with an entire sample ([The OBIS Manual](#)). An **Occurrence Extension** table provides **additional information about the occurrences** associated with each sampling event (e.g., taxonomic information, individual counts). An **extendedMeasurementOrFact Extension** table can be combined with an Event Core and an Occurrence Extension and, by accepting both *eventID* and *occurrenceID*, **allows abiotic and biotic measurements to be linked to events and to occurrences** (De Pooter et al., 2017).

As previously mentioned, **DwC standards** require that all column headers in each DwC table be appropriately matched to **Darwin Core terminology**. To ensure that all fields are mapped to DwC terms, occurrences must be organized in a **tidy format**. This means that **each occurrence should be represented by a single row** in the Occurrence table, rather than using a wide format where each occurrence is placed in a separate column (Fig. 3). The same is true for the eMoF table, where **each measurement or fact corresponds to a single row**.

A)	Taxon A	Taxon B	Taxon C
Sample 1	1	3	
Sample 2	2	1	1
Sample 3	1		2

.....>

B)	Taxa	Count
Sample 1	A	1
Sample 1	B	3
Sample 2	A	2
Sample 2	B	1
Sample 2	C	1
Sample 3	A	1
Sample 3	C	2

Fig. 3. Representation of a dataset in a wide-format (A) in comparison to a tidy-format (B).

Event tables can be constructed according to a **hierarchical structure** if applicable (Fig. 4), with events organised as **parent-child relationships** ([The OBIS Manual](#)). This structure helps avoid redundancy, as information common to all child events can be summarised in the parent event record. In OBIS, whenever information is absent in the child event, that information is inherited from the corresponding parent event. However, this is not true for GBIF, where child event cells without information will be treated as empty.

parentEventID	eventID	Km on effort	Temperature (°C)
	Site 1	10	
	Site 2	12	
Site 1	Site 1:Sample 1	10	16.5
Site 1	Site 1:Sample 2	10	16.0
Site 2	Site 2:Sample 1	12	15.8

Fig. 4. Example of a table organised based on a hierarchical structure between events. OBIS transfers information from parent events to child events (light grey), while GBIF does not.

In DwC tables, each sample or observation should be assigned its own unique **eventID**, while each occurrence should be assigned its own **occurrenceID**. These ID fields must remain constant and be globally unique. If an eventID or occurrenceID does not already exist, these can be generated by combining data already present in the dataset. Including the parent event in the child event ID (e.g., “Site_1:Sample_1”, with “Site_1” as the parent Event) might aid in understanding the dataset structure ([The OBIS Manual](#)).

Regarding data formatting, the DwC standard requires **latitude** and **longitude** to be in decimal degrees and referenced to the [WGS84](#) coordinate system (EPSG:4326). Furthermore, **date-related** fields must be ISO 8601 compliant. Hence, dates should be formatted as yyyy-mm-dd (e.g., 2026-04-27). In case the information about the time is also present, it should be formatted as hh:mm:ss (e.g., 16:25:38Z), separated from the date by a “T” (i.e., yyyy-mm-ddThh:mm:ss). Time should be followed by a time zone code (Z for UTC). Please refer to the [Darwin Core List of Terms](#) for more examples.

Taxonomic information must be validated against a taxonomic backbone. This process allows correction of minor misspellings, clarification of naming ambiguities, and assignment of identifiers such as Life Science Identifiers (LSID) to taxonomic names.

Measurements or facts in the eMoF table should be populated following controlled vocabularies (**BODC-NERC controlled vocabulary**). **measurementTypeID**, **measurementValueID**, and **measurementUnitID** should be filled with a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) given in the BODC vocabulary database (Fig. 5). It is also recommended to populate **measurementType**, **measurementValue**, and **measurementUnit** with the “preferred label” given in each BODC vocabulary page.

Fig. 5. Schematic workflow for the creation of an eMoF table (A), including the transformation into a tidy format (1) and the use of controlled vocabulary (2). Example of a BODC-NERC vocabulary page with the preferred label and Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) identified (B).

DATA PREPARATION TO UPLOAD TO THE AURORA Shiny App

THE APPLICATION CAN ASSIST WITH

Raw data can be imported into the **AURORA Shiny App** as a single flat table that contains all the information. The **AURORA Shiny App** allows you to **structure the dataset into the appropriate Darwin Core tables** (see Darwin Core Tables). The **AURORA Shiny App** can convert datasets organised in a wide format (i.e., where each event is represented by a row and each taxon is represented by a column) into a tidy format (Fig. 3; see Data Ingestion). Additionally, the **AURORA Shiny App** allows for matching the original column headers to the corresponding **DwC terms** (see Mapping Column Names to a DwC term).

The original dataset can be uploaded with **date-related fields** and **geographical coordinates** in multiple formats. The application will try to **transform** these into the appropriate standards: date fields will comply with **ISO 8601**, provided certain requirements are met (see Requirements Prior to the Data Ingestion), and geographical coordinates will be converted into **decimal degrees** and referenced to the **WGS84 datum** if needed. For more details, see the sections on Formatting coordinates and dates.

Additionally, if not already present, unique **ID fields** (*occurrenceID*, *eventID*, and *parentEventID*) can be created in the **AURORA Shiny App** using the information available in the existing columns (see Create Fields). The **AURORA Shiny App** also enables users to combine information from multiple columns that lack a corresponding DwC term to create **remarks fields**. Fields such as **basisOfRecord** and **geodeticDatum** can also be created within the **AURORA Shiny App**, considering that these fields will be populated with the same values for all records (see Create basisOfRecord and Coordinate System, respectively). If fields such as **organismQuantity** and **sampleSizeValue** are present in the mapped dataset, the **AURORA Shiny App** also supports creating the **dependency fields (e.g., organismQuantityType)** required (see Create Fields).

The **AURORA Shiny App** validates **taxonomic data**, removing ambiguities. Additionally, it allows for the retrieval of related information, such as the **Life Science Identifier (LSID)** for the matched taxa, which populates the *scientificNameID* field, as well as details about taxonomic ranking (e.g., Kingdom); see Taxonomy Tab. To match taxonomic names, the tool requires that only taxonomic information be provided. Users can **clean the original taxonomic data** by moving identification qualifiers into the *identificationQualifier* field in the application before performing taxonomic matching, while still preserving the original identifications (see Identification Data Cleaning).

Additionally, the **AURORA Shiny App** enables users to modify the original measurements or designations of facts using controlled vocabularies and link the corresponding IDs.

REQUIREMENTS PRIOR TO THE DATA INGESTION

The raw data can be uploaded as a **CSV file**. Full compatibility with **AURORA Shiny App** features requires that the dataset meet specific structural prerequisites before ingestion.

DATASET STRUCTURE

The dataset might already be structured in a tidy format, with each occurrence in a single row (Fig. 6.A) or it should be structured in a way that allows the platform to **convert it to a tidy format**, i.e., in a **wide format** – each row representing a single event, with occurrences corresponding to column headers (Fig. 6.B). The dataset may already be organised in a tidy format, with each occurrence presented in a single row (Fig. 6.A). If that is not the case, the raw data should be organised so that the platform can **convert it into a tidy format**. For example, in a wide format, where each row represents a single event and occurrences are spread across separate columns (Fig. 6.B). Any other formats, such as occurrences logged per row but grouped (Fig. 6.C), should be converted to one of the previously specified layouts before being ingested into the application.

Fig. 6. Accepted (A, B, i, and ii) and not accepted (C) data structures for upload in the AURORA Shiny App.

CONTROLLED VOCABULARIES FOR MEASUREMENTS OR FACTS

The platform can also structure measurements in a tidy format in the eMoF table. However, the user is responsible for identifying which columns correspond to measurements associated with occurrences and/or with events. Furthermore, the **measurements in the eMoF table** need to be populated using controlled vocabularies, which can be accomplished within the **AURORA Shiny App** (see Expected General data Structure). Although it is the user's responsibility to **identify the correct vocabulary** that matches the original terminology, using the **BODC-NERC controlled vocabulary** lists as a reference.

ORIGINAL COORDINATE REFERENCE SYSTEM

The original geographical information's **coordinate reference system** must be known and indicated to enable the **AURORA Shiny App** to **convert the coordinates** to decimal degrees and the WGS84 datum.

DWC TERM SELECTION

As mentioned earlier, fields can be **mapped to DwC terms** using the **AURORA Shiny App**, which attempts to match the original terms to the DwC terms. However, it is the **user's responsibility to verify and select the correct DwC terms** that correspond to the original dataset column names.

INFORMATION FOR ID FIELDS

The **AURORA Shiny App** can **create ID fields**, such as *eventID* or *occurrenceID*, by using existing dataset fields and appending a sequential numeric suffix to the combined values of selected columns (e.g., XPT_ABC_1). If the raw dataset does not contain the information needed to create those fields, or if the ID field corresponds to an external identifier, then either the ID field itself or the necessary information to generate it must be added to the raw dataset before it is ingested into the **AURORA Shiny App**.

MAIN FEATURES

DATA INGESTION TAB

DATA INGESTION

Data can be uploaded to the **AURORA Shiny App** by selecting the appropriate CSV file from the local device. The characteristics of the file, such as the **encoding**, **delimiter**, and whether the dataset includes a **header** row, should be specified before **loading the dataset**.

Fig. 7. The Ingest page of the AURORA Shiny App allows users to upload data into the application (steps 1-3). After uploading, users can preview the data (step 4) and, if necessary, transform it into a tidy format (step 5). Users can then inspect the main characteristics of the output dataset (step 6) before completing the ingestion process (step 7).

PREVIEW

The original dataset can be verified for accuracy in the **Raw Data** tab. The **Tidy/Pivot** tab allows transforming the raw dataset into a tidy format if required (see The raw data can be uploaded as a **CSV file**. Full compatibility with **AURORA Shiny App** features requires that the dataset meet specific structural prerequisites before ingestion.

Dataset Structure in Requirements Prior to the Data Ingestion). To do so, select the columns to be pivoted to a tidy format in the **Columns to pivot box**. For instance, considering Fig. 3.A, the columns *Taxon A*, *Taxon B*, and *Taxon C* should be selected at this step to obtain a tidy format table (Fig. 3.B). The name of the column created from the names of the pivoted columns can be specified in the box **Name for the new column (e.g., species) of former headers**, while the name of the column created from the data stored in cell values in the pivoted columns can be specified in **New column name (e.g., density) for previous cell values**. The user can then **Pivot** the dataset to convert it and inspect the output in **Current dataset preview**. If the raw dataset is already in a tidy format upon upload, the user can skip this step.

The **Column Summary** tab provides an overview of each column in the raw dataset or the converted, pivoted dataset. It includes the column name, the data type category (e.g., character, numeric), the number of missing values, and the count of unique entries.

Once the dataset is correctly imported, verified, and pivoted if necessary (Fig. 3), the user can finalise the ingest and move on to the next step.

FIELD MAPPING TAB

VALIDATION

Some terms in DwC are optional based on data type, while others are mandatory or highly recommended by major biodiversity data repositories, such as GBIF, OBIS, and EMODnet Biology. These, however, can be repository specific. Appendix A – Required and Strongly Suggested DwC Fields includes a summary of the terms required and strongly suggested according to GBIF, OBIS, and EMODnet Biology for further consultation.

At the top of the **Field Mapping** tab, the **AURORA Shiny App** analyses the imported dataset and notifies the user of any required terms that are missing after DwC term mapping. To adjust the set of required terms to consider, users should select the intended dataset submission repository from the **Target data repository** dropdown menu (Fig. 8). It also alerts the user about repeated field names during mapping.

Fig. 8. Interface of the AURORA Shiny App’s Field Mapping tab: The automatic (1) or manual mapping of Darwin Core terms (2), create new ID, remarks, and dependency fields (3), format geographical coordinates and date-related fields (4), and preview the resulting mapped dataset (5) and any errors and warnings that may have occurred during the process (6).

MAPPING COLUMN NAMES TO A DwC TERM

The Mapping section presents an interactive mapping of the column headers to **DwC terms**. An automatic suggestion of terms is available through the **Auto-suggest** button, by fuzzy matching the original names with the available DwC terms. However, it **is highly recommended to thoroughly review the automatically mapped terms**.

The **AURORA Shiny App** also enables **manually mapping** each original column name by selecting the most appropriate matching DwC term from the drop-down menu. The definition and examples of each selected term are available by clicking the ⓘ symbol.

Changes are saved only after the user clicks the **Apply Mapping** button at the bottom of the mapping table. This action may take a few seconds to complete.

CREATE FIELDS

This subsection supports the creation of ID and remarks fields using existing columns in the dataset (see Information for ID fields in Requirements Prior to the Data Ingestion), along with related dependency fields.

CREATE ID AND REMARK FIELDS

The user can select which ID field/remarks field should be created in the **Target field/Remarks field**, respectively. Next, the user should specify which columns to use for creating the new field in the **Source columns** section and indicate the separator to use for concatenating information from different source columns in the **Separator** box. When creating ID fields, users can also add a sequential numeric suffix to the generated text string. This allows, for instance, the creation of *occurrenceID* based on the *eventID*, while ensuring a unique ID for each occurrence, even if they share the same event.

If the field specified is already mapped in the dataset (i.e., *occurrenceID*, *eventID*), selecting **Overwrite target if it already exists** will replace it with the new version created by clicking **Create/update ID/remarks field**. The **AURORA Shiny App** allows multiple target fields per section. For instance, the user can generate the *occurrenceID* after having created the *eventID*.

CREATE basisOfRecord

The field *basisOfRecord* is required simultaneously by the three main biodiversity repositories (i.e., GBIF, OBIS, EMODnet Biology). The application allows users to create a *basisOfRecord* during workflow by selecting the appropriate vocabulary from the dropdown menu. Please note that this option will apply the selected value to all records in the dataset. If not, all records share the same *basisOfRecord*, the field must be filled out before importing the dataset into the application.

If this field is already present and mapped in the dataset, it can be either overwritten or this step can be skipped.

organismQuantity AND sampleSizeValue DEPENDENCY FIELDS

Some DwC fields require the presence of dependency fields in the dataset. These include *organismQuantity*, which requires the field *organismQuantityType*, and *sampleSizeValue*, which requires the field *sampleSizeUnit*. If one of these fields is present in the dataset but the dependency field is not, the application offers the user the option to create the missing field, provided it corresponds to a constant value. The user can **Create dependency field** after selecting the target association in **Dependency** and indicating the value to populate the new field in **Value to fill the missing dependency field**.

FORMATTING COORDINATES AND DATES

The **AURORA Shiny App** facilitates the conversion of geographic coordinates and dates and times to the formats required by the Darwin Core.

COORDINATE SYSTEM

According to DwC, geographical coordinates need to be in decimal degrees and referenced to EPSG:[4326]. If latitude and longitude are recorded in any other format, they will need to be converted to decimal degrees format. To do so, the user needs to indicate which Coordinate Reference System (CRS) the original coordinates are referenced to in the **Input CRS EPSG:[]** box (Original Coordinate Reference System in Requirements Prior to the Data Ingestion).

If the **Preserve original coordinates in verbatimLatitude and verbatimLongitude** checkbox is selected, these two new columns will be created and populated with the coordinates before the transformation to the new format. If the geographical coordinates are already in decimal degrees and the user selects this option, verbatimLatitude and verbatimLongitude will not be created. The **Create/fill geodeticDatum** checkbox creates a new column populated with the CRS. Since the target CRS for the conversion is always EPSG:4326, which is the datum required by DwC standards, this field will be populated with **WGS84**.

DATE FORMATTING

Dates and times can also be converted to ISO-8601, the required format for DwC, by selecting the **Standardise eventDate to ISO-8601** checkbox. The original date format should also be specified, indicating whether the day precedes the month (**dd/mm**) or vice versa (**mm/dd**). For instance, on 01/02/2024, if the dd/mm option is selected, that value is interpreted as 1 February 2024. If mm/dd is selected instead, it is interpreted as 2 January 2024. Dates already in ISO format, such as 2024-02-01 or 2019-10-01T22:39:12, will not be affected.

APPLY FORMATTING AND PREVIEW

At the end of the **Formatting** tab, the user should **Apply Formatting and Preview**. This action will highlight missing required terms, if any.

PREVIEW AND ISSUES

The **Preview** tab displays the dataset after the fields have been mapped to DwC terms, geographical coordinates and date-related fields have been formatted, and any additional fields have been created. The **Warnings/Errors**

section (Appendix B – List of Errors and Warnings from Field Mapping) provides information about any errors or warnings that may have occurred during the mapping or formatting process.

IDENTIFICATION DATA CLEANING TAB

The **AURORA Shiny App** supports validating taxonomic information in the dataset by matching it to a taxonomic backbone (WoRMS or GBIF Taxonomic Backbone). However, that matching requires a column with **clean taxonomic names** (Fig. 9). The **Identification Data Cleaning** tab of the **AURORA Shiny App** helps users organise taxonomic information by isolating the scientific names in the *scientificName* column for accurate matching purposes. Additionally, any other relevant information can be separated into corresponding columns, such as *identificationQualifier*, *lifeStage*, *sex*, *vitality*. For traceability, the original identification will be preserved in the *verbatimIdentification* field.

The screenshot shows the 'Identification Data Cleaning' tab in the AURORA Shiny App. The main content area contains instructions on Darwin Core standards for scientific names and a warning to review entries for accuracy. Below this are two panels: 'Settings' and 'Editable lookup table'. The 'Editable lookup table' displays a table with columns for currentScientificName, suggestedScientificName, useSuggestion, reviewedScientificName, and identificationQualifier. The table shows four rows of taxonomic entries, with the 'reviewedScientificName' column highlighted in red.

Settings

Source column used for grouping: *scientificName*

verbatimIdentification was not available with values, so the module is using *scientificName* as the source column.

Use the table on the side to edit rows corresponding to unique taxonomic entries.

Optional fields to include/edit

identificationQualifier

Build Editable Table Apply all suggestions

Editable lookup table

36 unique identification entries available for review. 0 reviewed *scientificName* cells are still missing.

Search:

currentScientificName	suggestedScientificName	useSuggestion	reviewedScientificName	identificationQualifier
Actiniaria msp 1	Actiniaria	Use	Actiniaria	
Actiniaria msp 2	Actiniaria	Use	Actiniaria	
Amphipoda indet.	Amphipoda	Use	Amphipoda	
Amphipoda msp 1	Amphipoda	Use	Amphipoda	

Fig. 9. Identification Data Cleaning interface enables users to create or modify unique scientific names and complete additional Darwin Core terms by extracting and refining information originally found in the *scientificName* or *verbatimIdentification* fields (e.g., *identificationQualifier*).

If the *scientificName* is already present in the mapped dataset, it will be preserved in the *verbatimIdentification* field if this field does not already exist. However, if both the *verbatimIdentification* and *scientificName* fields are

present in the dataset, please note that the *verbatimIdentification* will be preserved while the *scientificName* will be overwritten during this process.

The **AURORA Shiny App** will display all unique taxonomic combinations in the dataset and the user will **need to review each entry** before matching it to WoRMS or the GBIF Taxonomic Backbone. Values can be edited by double-clicking the respective cell or automatically replaced with the suggested correction (Fig. 10). Users can also choose specific DwC fields that have not yet been mapped to collect additional information from the input taxonomic data. If the scientific names are already formatted correctly, users can skip this step.

currentScientific Name	reviewedScientific Name	identificationQualifier	lifeStage	sex
Animalia indet	Animalia	indet		
Mola mola	Mola mola			
Mola cf. mola	Mola	cf. mola		
Mola	Mola			
Mola mola male	Mola mola			male
Mola mola (juv)	Mola mola		juvenile	

Fig. 10. Example schema of the Identification Data Cleaning interface. Users validate taxonomic entries via manual cell editing or automated suggestions. The interface allows for custom Darwin Core field mapping to capture additional data.

TAXONOMY TAB

In the **Taxonomy** tab, the **AURORA Shiny App** will match each unique *scientificName* with records from the selected taxonomic database (Fig. 11). The user can choose whether the application should use the **WoRMS** or the **GBIF Backbone Taxonomy**, depending on the type of data being handled (marine or terrestrial, respectively). The output for each unique input names can either be an exact match (i.e., the input name matches one record from the taxonomic database), an ambiguous match (i.e., when the input name matches more than one record), or a not-found match. Fuzzy matching is available, which enables small misspellings to be corrected.

Fig. 11. Preview of options and information available in the Taxonomy tab of the AURORA Shiny App. The interface enables users to select the taxonomic backbone for matching, provides details on the retrieved information, and outlines fields that correspond to Darwin Core terms which can be selected for retention.

Once **Run match** is complete, a summary of the results will be displayed. This summary includes details such as the total number of input names, the counts of exact matches, ambiguous matches, and names that were not found. It also specifies which input names did not yield any matches and indicates whether the taxonomic match has been applied to the main dataset. In the section Columns to **Keep in the Final Dataset**, users can select which columns from the taxonomic record output they wish to retain in the main dataset. Only columns that have a corresponding DwC term are available for selection.

For each ambiguous match, the user can select which of the records is the correct match in the **choice column** of the **Lookup table** (Fig. 12). Once a record is selected for an ambiguous match, the user will be asked to confirm their choice which will be applied to all the occurrences that share the same *scientificName*. If none of the displayed records are correct, the user must revise and correct the taxonomic information before data ingestion. A summary of the Lookup table can also be **downloaded as a CSV file**.

inputName	Taxon Match Status	Scientific Name	Taxonomic Status	Taxon Rank	kingdom	class	scientificNameID
Polychaeta	Found	Polychaeta	accepted	Class	Animalia	Polychaeta	urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:883
Zoantharia	Ambiguous	<input type="text" value="Zoantharia"/>					
		Zoantharia	accepted	Order	Animalia	Hexacorallia	urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:607338
		Zoantharia	unaccepted	Class	Animalia	Zoantharia	urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:1364
Tubulariidae	Found	Tubulariidae	accepted	Family	Animalia	Hydrozoa	urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:1603
Aconema	Ambiguous	<input type="text" value="Aconema"/>					
		Aconema	unaccepted	Genus	Chromista	Bicosoecophyceae	urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:369313
		Aponema	accepted	Genus	Animalia	Chromadorea	urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:2363
		Aronema	accepted	Genus	Animalia	Enoplea	urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:582855
		Asconema	accepted	Genus	Animalia	Hexactinellida	urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:132122
		Abunema	junior subjective synonym	Genus	Animalia	Enoplea	urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:227361
Canis lupus	Not Found						

Fig. 12. Example of the taxonomic validation process interface using WoRMS. The output includes the validated scientificName and its corresponding scientificNameID, which will be included in the main database. Users can also choose optional fields such as rank, kingdom, and class. In cases of ambiguous matches (for example, "Zoantharia" or "Aconema"), the interface allows users to manually select the correct taxonomic record.

Once all unique scientific names are validated, apply the changes by clicking 'Apply to dataset' at the bottom of the lookup table. A warning will be displayed if there are unresolved ambiguous matches. The user can choose to either keep the ambiguous match or cancel it and resolve the issue. If an ambiguous match is kept unresolved, those records will be excluded from the dataset.

DARWIN CORE TABLES TAB

In **Darwin Core Tables** tab, the **AURORA Shiny App** allows for splitting a flat table into Darwin Core tables. User can choose which fields to retain in the Event, Occurrence, and eMoF tables based on whether they want to generate tables for a **Sampling event (Event core)** or an **Occurrence (Occurrence core)** (Fig. 13). **Required fields** are automatically selected based on the selected biodiversity repository (i.e., GBIF, OBIS, or EMODnet Biology). Strongly recommended fields are preselected and can be deselected, while recommended or optional fields can still be selected.

To create an eMoF table, the user should indicate which columns correspond to measurements or facts associated with events in the **Columns to move to eMoF (event level)** box and which measurements or facts are associated with occurrences in the **Columns to move to eMoF (occurrences level)**. Besides being included

in the eMoF table, certain measurements or facts can also remain in the Event or Occurrence table as long as they can be mapped to the appropriate DwC term ([The OBIS Manual](#)). For instance, if the user adds *organismQuantity* to the **Columns to move to eMoF (occurrence level)**, this column can be included in the Occurrence table, but the information will also be added as a measurement in the eMoF table.

Build Darwin Core Tables

Choose the archive resource type and review the allowed fields step by step before building the Darwin Core tables.

Build settings

Resource type

Sampling event (Event core)

Occurrence (Occurrence core)

Repository rules currently applied: GBIF. Active architecture: Sampling event (Event core). Required fields are included automatically and are not shown here. Strongly recommended fields start selected. Recommended and optional fields start unselected.

Event **Occurrence** **eMoF**

Selection warnings / status

Current selections — Event: 5 field(s); Occurrence: 7 field(s); eMoF event: 1 field(s); eMoF occurrence: 0 field(s).

Step 1 — Event table

Required fields are included automatically and are not shown here. Only non-required fields are selectable below.

Search terms

Type to filter terms

decimalLatitude strongly recommended

Fig. 13. Overview of the Build Darwin Core Tables tab, featuring selectable resource types (1) and a window for selecting which Darwin Core (DwC) terms to retain in each corresponding DwC table (2)

When you click **Build Darwin Core tables**, the **AURORA Shiny App** creates the Event, Occurrence, and eMoF tables from the selected mappings. The resulting tables can be reviewed in the preview sections. If any changes are needed, click the **Start Over** button. You will then need to select again the fields to retain in each Darwin Core table and click **Build Darwin Core tables** again.

eMoF EDITOR TAB

In this **eMoF Editor** tab, the user will have the option to fill each unique original designation of measurement and facts with the corresponding **BODC-NERC controlled vocabulary**. The tool will present every unique combination of measurement type and value, provided the value is categorical. The values of *measurementType* and *measurementValue* can then be edited to the corresponding controlled vocabularies identified by the user (Fig.

14). If the *measurementValue* are numeric, they will be locked to prevent accidental bulk edits.. Values for *measurementUnit* can also be entered at this step. *measurementTypeID*, *measurementValueID*, and *measurementUnitID* should be set to the associated URL of the vocabulary used (Fig. 5).

measurementType	measurementTypeID	measurementValue	measurementValueID	measurementUnit	measurementUnitID
Temp (°C)		(numeric)			
organismQuantity		(numeric)			
lifeStage		juv.			
lifeStage		Adult			
samplingProtocol		A			
samplingProtocol		B			

↓

measurementType	measurementTypeID	measurementValue	measurementValueID	measurementUnit	measurementUnitID
Temperature of the water body by the in-sity thermometer	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/PSSSTS01/	(numeric)		Degrees Celsius	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UPAA/
Count of biological entity specified elsewhere	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/LSTAGE01/	(numeric)		Dimensionless	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/UUUU/
lifeStage	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/OCOUNT01/	juvenile	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S11/current/S1127/	Not applicable	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/XXXX/
lifeStage	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/OCOUNT01/	adult	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S11/current/S1116/	Not applicable	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/XXXX/
Sampling protocol	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/SAMPPROT/	A		Not applicable	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/XXXX/
Sampling protocol	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/SAMPPROT/	B		Not applicable	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/XXXX/

Fig. 14. eMoF Editor interface enables users to edit cell values and fill them as needed.

DwC TABLES OVERVIEW & QC TAB

The **DwC Tables Overview & QC** tab summarizes the data description and quality control for DwC tables. For a thorough evaluation, a complete quality control check should be conducted using the [LifeWatch and EMODnet Biology QC tool](#) after exporting DwC tables.

The **Data Overview** section displays the export status (Fig. 15), record counts, eMoF summaries, a temporal distribution of event dates, an interactive map to inspect record distribution, and a plot of the taxonomic hierarchy. The **Issues found** section includes summaries of detailed issue logs (e.g., issues related to eMoFs).

If no errors are detected, the export status in **Data Overview** will indicate "OK" and the DwC tables can be exported as a ZIP archive containing the cleaned CSV tables. However, if errors are present, exportation will not be permitted.

Fig. 15. Interface Darwin Core (DwC) Tables Overview & QC tab, providing a summary of DwC tables data and quality control.

METADATA FORM

In the **Metadata** section, the **AURORA Shiny App** provides the option to pre-fill a metadata form oriented toward publication. The sections and fields included are based on the metadata requirements set by the **GBIF IPT** for publishing the Darwin Core Archive. All mandatory fields are marked with an asterisk (Fig. 16).

By completing this form, users can export it in .odt format and open it in spreadsheet software such as Excel. This process makes it easier for dataset authors to review and make corrections. After the revisions are made, the metadata can then be copied into the IPT metadata form.

AURORA Shiny App Home Ingest Field Mapping Identification Data Cleaning Taxonomy Darwin Core Tables eMoF Editor DwC Tables Overview & QC **Metadata** About

Dataset Metadata

The sections follow the structure of the GBIF IPT metadata form. Fields can be completed to facilitate metadata review among dataset authors, and then copied and pasted into the metadata form of the selected IPT for dataset submission.

- Basic Metadata** (Selected)
- Contacts
- Acknowledgements
- Geographical Coverage
- Taxonomic Coverage
- Temporal Coverage
- Additional Description
- Keywords
- Project Data
- Sampling Methods
- Citations
- Collection Data
- External Links
- Additional Metadata

Resource identity

Title *
test
Título descritivo do recurso.

Short Name Publishing Organization *
Ex.: aurora_megafauna_2019 [Dropdown]
Nome curto do recurso. Organização responsável pela publicação do recurso.

Resource type

Type * Subtype Update Frequency *
[Dropdown] [Dropdown] [Dropdown]
Opção inspirada na folha info da planilha.

Languages and licence

Data Language * Metadata Language * Data Licence *

Fig. 16. Metadata form designed to prefill dataset information, streamlining authors' review and validation.

ABOUT THE AURORA PROJECT

The **AURORA Shiny App** was developed as a core output of the project **AURORA - bringing deep-sea biodiversity data to light**, an initiative dedicated to streamline the mobilization of deep-sea biodiversity data.

While the deep sea covers 65% of the planet, it remains the least understood biome on Earth. In European marine waters, deep-sea records (>200 m) account for only 11% of databases like the Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS) — a figure that plunges to just 1% for depths below 3,500 meters. To address this knowledge gap, the Digital Marine Biodiversity Lab at the University of Aveiro is mobilising its collections of deep-sea data, starting with the Aurora seamount on the Gakkel Ridge in the Central Arctic Ocean.

The AURORA project is funded through the [DTO-BioFlow](#) project, contributing directly to the development of the European Digital Twin of the Ocean.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A – REQUIRED AND STRONGLY SUGGESTED DwC FIELDS

Table 1. Classification of required and strongly recommended terms by DwC table and biodiversity repository.

DwC Tables	Event Core			Occurrence Extension			eMoF Extension			Occurrence Core			Overall (flat table)		
	GBIF ¹	OBIS ²	EMODnet ³	GBIF ¹	OBIS ²	EMODnet ³	-	OBIS ²	EMODnet ³	GBIF ¹	OBIS ²	-	GBIF ¹	OBIS ²	EMODnet ³
basisOfRecord				■	■	■				■	■		■	■	■
datasetName			■												■
decimalLatitude	■	■	■	■						■	■		■	■	■
decimalLongitude	■	■	■	■						■	■		■	■	■
eventDate	■	■	■	■						■	■		■	■	■
eventID	■	■	■	■	■	■		■	■				■	■	■
institutionCode			■												■
measurementType								■	■					■	■
measurementTypeID								■	■					■	■
measurementUnit								■	■					■	■
measurementValue								■	■					■	■
occurrenceID				■	■	■		■	■	■	■		■	■	■
occurrenceStatus				■	■	■					■		■	■	■
samplingProtocol	■	■						■			■		■	■	■
scientificName				■	■	■				■	■		■	■	■
scientificNameID					■	■					■			■	■
kingdom				■	*	■				■	*		■	*	■
taxonRank				■	■	■				■	■		■	■	■
sampleSizeUnit	■	■						■			■		■	■	■
sampleSizeValue	■	■						■			■		■	■	■
samplingEffort	■	■						■			■		■	■	■
locationID	■	■								■	■		■	■	■
organismQuantity				■	■			■		■	■		■	■	■

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DwC Tables	Event Core			Occurrence Extension			eMoF Extension			Occurrence Core			Overall (flat table)		
	GBIF ¹	OBIS ²	EMODnet ³	GBIF ¹	OBIS ²	EMODnet ³	-	OBIS ²	EMODnet ³	GBIF ¹	OBIS ²	-	GBIF ¹	OBIS ²	EMODnet ³
Biodiversity database															
organismQuantityType															
countryCode		*									*			*	
geodeticDatum		*									*			*	
parentEventID															
footprintWKT															
footprintSRS															
individualCount															
coordinateUncertaintyInMeters															
maximumDepthInMeters															
minimumDepthInMeters															
measurementUnitID															
measurementValueID															
type															
eventType															
month															
year															
continent															
coordinatePrecision															
license															
genus															
order															
identificationQualifier															
measurementAccuracy															
measurementID															
measurementRemarks															
catalogNumber															
collectionCode															
modified															
scientificNameAuthorship															

¹ retrieved from the GBIF's [Occurrence Data](#) and [Sampling Event Data](#) templates, as of 2026-04-20

² retrieved from [The OBIS Manual](#), as of 2026-04-20

³ retrieved from the Ocean Teacher Global Academy (OTGA)'s course [Contributing Datasets to EMODnet Biology](#)

– no information available about the terms required or recommended for this type of DwC term, as of 01-2026

blue shading – Required term; **grey shading** – Strongly recommended term

* recommended by [The OBIS Manual](#) as unofficial mandatory terms

APPENDIX B – LIST OF ERRORS AND WARNINGS FROM FIELD MAPPING

Table 2. List of errors and warnings potentially retrieved by the AURORA Shiny App during field mapping to Darwin Core Terms.

Rule	Severity	Field	Description
coord_non_numeric	ERROR	decimalLatitude/decimalLongitude	Coordinates are not numeric or could not be parsed
coord_parse_missing_pkg	ERROR	decimalLatitude/decimalLongitude	Parsing required but 'parzer' package is not installed
depth_inconsistent	ERROR	minimumDepthInMeters/maximumDepthInMeters	Minimum depth is greater than maximum depth
empty_scientificName	ERROR	scientificName	scientificName is missing or empty
out_of_range	ERROR	decimalLatitude/decimalLongitude	Coordinates outside valid EPSG:4326 range
out_of_range_after	ERROR	decimalLatitude/decimalLongitude	Coordinates invalid after reprojection
reproject_failed	ERROR	decimalLatitude/decimalLongitude	CRS transformation failed
coord_missing	INFO	decimalLatitude/decimalLongitude	One or both coordinate fields missing
coord_original_system_disabled	INFO	coordinates	Coordinate processing disabled due to missing fields
coord_parzer	INFO	coordinates	Coordinates parsed successfully using parzer
date_iso	INFO	eventDate	eventDate standardized to ISO-8601
geodeticDatum_created	INFO	geodeticDatum	geodeticDatum field created
geodeticDatum_filled	INFO	geodeticDatum	Missing values filled with provided datum
name_trim	INFO	scientificName	Whitespace standardized in scientificName
option_blocked	INFO	various	Options ignored due to missing coordinate data
reproject_to_target	INFO	coordinates	Coordinates successfully reprojected

Rule	Severity	Field	Description
verbatim_created_from_decimalLatitude	INFO	verbatimLatitude	Original latitude preserved before transformation
verbatim_created_from_decimalLongitude	INFO	verbatimLongitude	Original longitude preserved before transformation
vocab_standardize	INFO	basisOfRecord/sex/lifeStage	Vocabulary standardized
coords_zero_zero	WARNING	decimalLatitude/decimalLongitude	Coordinates are (0,0) likely erroneous
date_parse	WARNING	eventDate	Could not standardize eventDate to ISO-8601
depth_negative	WARNING	minimumDepthInMeters/maximumDepthInMeters	Negative depth detected
duplicate_exact	WARNING	row	Exact duplicate row detected
empty_coordinates	WARNING	decimalLatitude/decimalLongitude	Missing coordinates after parsing